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Educational Administrators' Physical Abuse And Neglect Management Strategies As Correlates Of Depression Reduction Among Elderly Persons In University Of Port Harcourt Teaching Hospital

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ABSTRACT

The study investigated relationship between elder abuse and depression among elderly persons in University of Port Harcourt Teaching Hospital (UPTH). A sample of 500 elderly patients was used for the study drawn from a population of all elderly patients within the hospital premises who must have attained the age of 60 years above as the time of this study. Purposive and convenience sampling techniques were used to draw the sample. Five research questions were answered while five corresponding null hypotheses were tested in the study at 0.05 level of significance. Two instruments were used for the study which are the Elderly Depression Scale (EDS) and Elder Abuse Questionnaire (EAQ). The instruments were validated by the research supervisor and experts in measurement and evaluation. The reliability of the instruments was estimated using the Cronbach Alpha reliability method of internal consistency. Data were analyzed using simple regression and t-test associated with regression. The Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 23 was used for the analysis. Findings revealed among others that there is a strong positive relationship between physical abuse and depression among elderly persons in UPTH. It was also revealed that there is a very weak positive relationship between sexual abuse and depression among elderly persons in UPTH. Based on the findings, it was recommended among others that the government and hospital management should create specialized elder abuse reporting mechanisms and increasing staff training to recognize and prevent abuse.

Keywords: Physical Abuse, Elder Abuse, Management strategies Neglect, Depression.

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Depression is one of the most common mental health disorders worldwide, affecting people of all ages, genders and backgrounds. Among the elderly, however, depression poses unique challenges and is often under-recognized and undertreated. Depression in older adults can significantly affect their quality of life, impair physical health and even increase mortality risk. Depression in elderly persons is often characterized by persistent sadness, feelings of hopelessness, a lack of interest in activities and various physical symptoms. Unlike younger individuals, depression in older adults is more likely to be misdiagnosed or dismissed as a natural consequence of aging, grief or physical illness. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), depression affects approximately 7% of the elderly population globally, but this figure is likely underestimated due to the challenges in diagnosis

and reporting. Research indicates that depression affects approximately 10-20% of older adults in Nigeria (Adeyemo et al., 2016).

Relationship between physical abuse and depression among elderly persons

Physical Abuse occurs when a considerable level of force is used on an elderly person to cause unnecessary pain or injury. It is the infliction of pain or injury, physical coercion even when the reason is to help the older person. Examples of physical abuse include beating, pushing, kicking, pinching, burning, shoving, drug-induced restraints, over-or under –medicating, depriving the older person of food as punishment and exposing the person to severe weather. Many of these occur within the family but are most times unreported. The elderly are physical abused daily by trusted caregivers. Due to old age older persons become physically and mentally dependent. This increases the incidence of physical abuse. Most personal duties they can no longer perform by themselves. They are also too weak and frail to defend or fight back when abused. A wheel chair-bound, elderly man shared his experience on the mistreatment he daily received from the houseboy (male servant) employed to take care of him. He recounted that most times the mood of the boy determined the level of physical abuse he suffered. Said he, “The violent pushing of the wheelchair creates a lot of fear in me. Sometimes when I need to be exposed to some sunshine, the boy abandons me in the sun until such a time that is convenient for him to push me back into the house. I cannot complain to my only daughter who engaged the boy’s services because she once told me to endure all the mistreatment that getting a replacement could be very difficult. Care givers for the elderly are very difficult to secure.” There are quite a lot of older persons who suffer similar fate in the hands of trusted ones whom they depend on for care. Due to the level of respect accorded the elderly in Nigeria, it is uncommon to have cases of beatings and deliberate infliction of injury on the elderly. Though most injuries suffered by the older persons could be unintentional, the abused fear reporting to other members of the family even when evidence is available.

World Health Organization (WHO) referred that the age of 65 years is considered as a definition of 'elderly' or older person in developed countries. Even though this definition is considered somewhat illogical, mostly it is associated with receiving pension benefits. At present, United Nations (UN) does not make any standard numerical criterion, but the UN agreed above 60 years old referring older population. (WHO, 2014) Even though the definition of old age is used commonly, there is no general agreement about the exact age of elderly. Octavian, et al (2010) referred that World Health Organization examines that third aged group would be more appropriate than the elder or old persons as the aging process is a physiological system that is being specific to any life form throughout its existence, the old age representing the ontogenetic final stage. Generally, the main characteristic of old age people is showing signs of poly-pathology which need a multi-medication. The effect of this poli-pathology that is added to the aging physiological phenomenon is finally represented by the following states: incapacity, dependency handicap and infirmity (Octavian, et al., 2010).

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According to Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD), (2013) 18.5% population of Finland was over 65 years old and 5% of the Finnish population was over 80 years old in 2012. This percentage of Finnish population exceeds the OECD average where 15% of the population was over 65 years old and 4% of the population was over 80 years old. It is assuming that by 2050, 27% of the population in Finland will be over 65 years old and 11% of the population will be

over 80 years old, which is giving the signal that Finland is going to be the faster aging country than the OECD average. (OECD, 2013) According to Talala, et al. (2009), mental health problems, including depression, anxiety and psychological symptoms among the elderly in Finland, are as prevalent today as they were 20 years ago. About 5% of the general population in Finland are suffering from major depression. On the other hand, the prevalence of psychological distress among the elderly is close to 24% of the population. (Talala, et al., 2009).

Relationship between neglect and depression among elderly persons

Neglect means the failure of a caretaker to provide the goods or services, including medical services, which are necessary to avoid physical or emotional harm or pain. Exploitation includes a caretaker's illegal use of a senior's resources for monetary or personal benefit, profit, or gain. Elder neglect has been defined by the National Research Council as "an omission by responsible caregivers that constitutes neglect under applicable federal or state law" (NRC, 2003). Others have defined it as "the refusal or failure by those responsible to provide food, shelter, health care, or protection for a vulnerable elder" (National Center on Elder Abuse, 2013). The most common form of elder maltreatment is neglect. Neglect is defined as the failure of a caregiver to provide basic care to a patient and to provide goods and services necessary for living safely in a safe environment (Levine, 2003). Another accepted definition is the refusal or failure to fulfill any part of a person's obligation or duties to an elder (Dolan, 1999).

Over 65 aged people have over diagnosed arteriosclerosis and senility tendency in the USA, without recognizing that depression may manifest itself by a slowing of psychomotor activities. There are signs of brain disease if people have lowered intellectual function and a loss of interest in sex, hobbies, and activities. However, less than 10% of all depressions is psychotic depression that is relatively uncommon. There is an assumption that 15% to 30% of adults suffer clinical depressive episodes, most often of moderate severity, at some point at their lives, with the onset of depressive illness peaking in the 40s and 50s. However, only 25% of persons with symptoms of depression look for mental health professional attention. Furthermore, 50% to 80% of all suicides are occurred due to depression, and possibly 75% of all suicides is committed by psychiatric patients. (Stuart, 2013) Depression is the most common affective or mood disorder in old age. Approximately 15% of older adults suffer from depression, and among them 3% to 26% are elderly residents in the community. The prevalence of depression is higher among the hospitalized elderly patients (23%), and it ranges from 16% to 30% among nursing home inhabitants. (Smeltzer, et al., 2010).

Statement of the Problem

The current rate of elder abuse in University of Port Harcourt Teaching Hospital (UPTH) is alarming and calls for investigation. Elder abuse is an underreported social issue globally, with a particularly concerning prevalence in UPTH. The aging population in Nigeria is increasing rapidly, with a growing number of elderly individuals becoming exposed to various forms of abuse, including physical, emotional, financial and psychological maltreatment. Despite cultural norms that traditionally emphasized respect and care for older persons, modern socio-economic pressures, shifting family issues and weak social protection systems have led to a rise in elder abuse across the country. As a result, the elderly, who were once seen as custodians of wisdom and leadership, are now often neglected, isolated and mistreated by family members, caregivers and even the larger society. One of the most common consequences of elder abuse is its impact on mental health particularly depression. Depression is a common but often overlooked mental health condition among elderly persons, characterized by feelings of persistent sadness, hopelessness and a loss of interest in life. It is no doubt that when these elderly persons become abused, they experience depression and it could be observed by the researcher (A UPTH staff) that most of these elderly persons are abused especially by their caregivers. It could also be observed that less attention is given to elder persons by the government hence there is every chance that they may experience depression as a consequence of abuse. It is upon this backdrop the researcher intends to investigate the relationship between elder abuse and depression among elderly persons in University of Port Harcourt Teaching Hospital (UPTH).

Aim and Objectives of the Study

Specifically, the objectives of this study are:

1. To determine the relationship between physical abuse and depression among elderly persons in (UPTH)
2. To examine the relationship between neglect and depression among elderly persons in (UPTH)

Research Questions

The following research questions were answered in this study.

1. What is the extent of relationship between physical abuse and depression among elderly persons in (UPTH)?
2. What is the extent of relationship between neglect and depression among elderly persons in (UPTH)?

Hypotheses

The following corresponding null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance to guide this study.

1. There is no significant relationship between physical abuse and depression among elderly persons in (UPTH)
2. There is no significant relationship between neglect and depression among elderly persons in (UPTH)

METHODOLOGY

The design of this study is correlational research designs. The population of the study consists of all elderly patients within the hospital premises who must have attained the age of 60 years above as the time of this study. A sample of 500 elderly patients was used for the study. Purposive and convenience sampling techniques was used to draw the sample for the study. A total of 1200 instrument was distributed and only 572 respondents scored above 25 in the Elderly Depression Scale (EDS) which automatically qualified for the study, out of the 572 qualified respondents, only 500 respondents filled their instruments completely with errors and these formed the sample for the study. Two instruments were used for the study. They are the Elderly Depression Scale (EDS) and Elder Abuse Questionnaire (EAQ). The first section consists of the introductory part and the respondents' personal information. The EDS was used to measure the respondents' level of depression. The items were adapted from the 11-ITEM Kutcher Adolescent Depression Scale: (KADS-11, 2006). The reliability of the instruments was determined using the Cronbach Alpha reliability method of internal consistency. Reliability coefficients were obtained as follows: Elderly Depression Scale at 0.88, physical abuse at 0.82, neglect at 0.78 respectively. Research questions were answered using simple regression while their corresponding null hypotheses were tested using t-test associated with regression. The Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 23 was used for the analysis.

RESULTS

Data Presentation

Research Question 1: *What is the relationship between physical abuse and depression among elderly persons in (UPTH)?*

Table 4.1: Regression analysis of the relationship between physical abuse and depression among elderly persons in (UPTH)

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square
1	.624	.790	.788

Table 4.1 revealed that physical abuse and depression among elderly persons in (UPTH) obtained a correlation coefficient of $r = 0.624$ indicating a moderate positive relationship. In answer to the research question, an R Square of 0.790 was obtained and an adjusted R^2 value of 0.788. Based on the R^2 value of 0.790, it shows that 79% (0.790×100) of the variance in depression among elderly

persons can be explained by physical abuse, which is a substantial amount. This shows a strong relationship between physical abuse and depression among elderly persons in (UPTH).

Research Question 2: *What is the relationship between neglect and depression among elderly persons in (UPTH)?*

Table 4.2: Regression analysis of the relationship between neglect and depression among elderly persons in (UPTH)

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square
1	.527	.820	.818

Table 4.2 revealed that neglect and depression among elderly persons in (UPTH) obtained a correlation coefficient of $r = 0.527$ indicating a moderate positive relationship. In answer to the research question, an R Square of 0.820 was obtained and an adjusted R^2 value of 0.818. Based on the R^2 value of 0.820, it shows that 82% (0.820×100) of the variance in depression among elderly persons can be explained by neglect, which is a substantial amount. This shows a strong relationship between neglect and depression among elderly persons in (UPTH).

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant relationship between physical abuse and depression among elderly persons in (UPTH)

Table 4.3: Regression analysis of the relationship between physical abuse and depression among elderly persons in (UPTH)

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		
		B	Std. Error	Beta	T	Sig.
1	(Constant)	10.546	.836		12.622	.000
	Physical abuse	.739	.041	.624	17.829	.000

Table 4.3 revealed that the value of the constant a is 10.546 with standard error of .836 while the regression coefficient is .739 with standard error of .041. The value of the slope B after conversion to standardized coefficients produced a value of .624. The standardized coefficient of .624 is significant at (Sig.) .000. The value of the slope B converted to standardized coefficient is .624. The significance value (Sig.) is 0.000, which is less than the common alpha level of 0.05. This indicates that the result is statistically significant. Since the Sig. value is less than 0.05, the null hypothesis (H_0) is therefore rejected. This means that there is relationship between physical abuse and depression among elderly persons in (UPTH).

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant relationship between neglect and depression among elderly persons in (UPTH)

Table 4.4: Regression analysis of the relationship between neglect and depression among elderly persons in (UPTH)

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		
		B	Std. Error	Beta	T	Sig.
1	(Constant)	44.616	1.691		26.388	.000
	Neglect	.217	.042	.227	5.211	.000

Table 4.4 revealed that the value of the constant a is 44.616 with standard error of 1.691 while the regression coefficient is .217 with standard error of .042. The value of the slope B after conversion to standardized coefficients produced a value of .227. The standardized coefficient of .227 is significant at (Sig.) .000. The value of the slope B converted to standardized coefficient is .227. The significance value (Sig.) is 0.000, which is less than the common alpha level of 0.05. This indicates that the result is statistically significant. Since the Sig. value is less than 0.05, the null hypothesis (H_0) is therefore rejected. This means that there is relationship between neglect and depression among elderly persons in (UPTH).

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The findings of the study are discussed hereunder one by one.

Relationship between physical abuse and depression among elderly persons in (UPTH)

There is a strong positive relationship between physical abuse and depression among elderly persons in UPTH. It was also revealed that the relationship is statistically significant at (Sig.) .000 alpha level. This indicates that as physical abuse increases, the level of depression also tends to increase among elderly persons at UPTH. This finding was envisaged by the researcher because the pains inflicted alone would bring memories of the abuse thereby making the victim depressed. This finding agreed with that of Weissberger et.al. (2020) where they investigated physical and mental health correlates of perceived financial exploitation in older adults: Preliminary findings from the Finance, Cognition, and Health in Elders Study (FINCHES). Findings revealed that those who believed they were physically abused endorsed significantly greater symptoms of depression. Furthermore, this finding also agreed with Patel et.al. (2018) where they investigated prevalence and predictors of abuse in elderly patients with depression at a tertiary care Centre in Saurashtra, India. Among those who had experienced abuse, 50% had experienced psychological abuse, 17% had experienced neglect, 8% had experienced exploitation and 4% had experienced physical abuse. About 54% of patients with severe depression had experienced abuse. Daughters-in-law (54%) and sons (42%) were the most common perpetrators. Illiteracy and severe depression were found to be the predictors of abuse.

Relationship between neglect and depression among elderly persons in (UPTH)

There is a strong positive relationship between neglect and depression among elderly persons in UPTH. It was also revealed that the relationship is statistically significant at (Sig.) .000 alpha level. This indicates that as neglect increases, the level of depression also tends to increase among elderly persons at UPTH. This finding was envisaged by the researcher because when someone is neglected, they feel empty and helpless which will invariably cause depression. This finding agreed with that of Özer & Tanrıverdi (2023) where they investigated determining depression, abuse, and neglect in elderly individuals. Findings revealed that the elderly individuals who were exposed to physical and emotional abuse and neglect had higher mean depression scores compared to those who were not ($P < 0.05$). Furthermore, this finding also agreed with Dong, Simon, Odwazny & Gorbien (2008) where they investigated depression and elder abuse and neglect among a community-dwelling Chinese elderly population. Multiple logistic regression modeling showed that depression is independently associated with elder abuse and neglect (OR, 3.26; CI, 1.49–7.10, $p < 0.003$).

CONCLUSIONS

It was concluded that physical abuse, neglect and emotional abuse are the most common causes of depression among elder persons in UPTH. Financial exploitation does not necessarily make elderly persons depressed. Sexual abuse has no effect on the depression of elderly persons in UPTH.

RECOMMENDATIONS

From the findings of this study, the under listed recommendations were made:

1. The government and hospital management should create specialized elder abuse reporting mechanisms and increasing staff training to recognize and prevent abuse.
2. There should be a regular monitoring and home visits by healthcare professionals to ensure the elderly are receiving adequate care and attention.

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